

Data Unit Groups Implementation and Validation for Multi-Domain and Multi-Technology Deterministic 6G Systems

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Abstract—Deterministic systems fill the gap of providing end-to-end predictive networking capabilities across multiple domains and technologies for applications that have stringent Key Performance Indicator requirements, e.g. Industry 4.0 verticals. In this paper, a 6G solution is realised to enable deterministic networking for all IP traffic in a multi-domain and multi-technology environment. Special focus is given to a proposed data plane concept, called Data Unit Group, and the integration of a Data Unit Group-enabled DetNet router in an end-to-end Network Digital Twin-driven control plane, which manages the entire service provisioning ensuring deterministic Key Performance Indicators fulfilment. The proffered data plane solution and implementation has been validated in a lab testbed and shows that the realisation can operate at line speed without any networking performance impact.

I. INTRODUCTION AND STATE OF THE ART

Industries are looking to adopt 6G for its ability to meet high performance standards like low latency, high reliability, and predictable network behaviour. Following ITU-R's 2030 vision framework, 6G will offer flexible wireless solutions, making it ideal for sectors like Industry 4.0. The adoption of 6G and technologies like Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN)/DetNet will grow with deterministic networking solutions and their standards ensuring interoperability.

TSN and DetNet share similar objectives alongside packet treatment behaviours (Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability (FRER) for TSN and Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions (PREOF) for DetNet), but are positioned as different solutions, i.e. TSN being an IEEE technology for link-level capabilities while DetNet aims to offer deterministic networking as inter-connected computer networks [1]. TSN's FRER algorithms standardised in the IEEE 802.1 working group are explicitly mentioned in IETF's DetNet Working Group (WG) documents as the foundations for PREOF. However, DetNet goes further by offering a broader set of tools to achieve deterministic networking in inter-computer network environments. This is achieved by a range of RFCs (RFCs) in the DetNet WG to establish an end-to-end connection allowing intermediate nodes to perform specific PREOF actions over the service flow traversing multiple administrative and technology domains.

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Implementations of DetNet data plane solutions demonstrate it is feasible to bring deterministic networking to multi-domain and multi-technology networks [2], with the ambition to see deterministic networking being fully integrated in cellular networks [3]. This forms the basis for the work published in this paper which aims at bringing deterministic networking capability for all Internet Protocol (IP) traffic without the need of dedicated tunnels and the additional benefit of allowing deterministic packet treatment across a set of packets that carry a single Application Data Unit (ADU), as contributed by the authors to the DetNet WG [4].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the proposed solution for IP-based traffic traversing DetNet-enabled administrative and technology domains. This is followed by Section III, which provides a detailed conceptual description of the control and data plane implementation. Section IV then validates the implementation to demonstrate that the DetNet router performs without any network performance degradation. The paper is concluded in Section V.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This section presents the system architecture for a deterministic data plane which introduces a Packet Data Unit (PDU)-like concept for all IP traffic and a corresponding multi-domain control plane. The overarching system architecture is provided in Fig. 1 which illustrates the two domains 3GPP and DetNet as a representation of multiple domains and technologies. Note that the 3GPP domain is considered to be DetNet-enabled, following the considerations in 3GPP's TS 23.501 specification [5].

In case of a 3GPP domain, the 5G System (5GS) is exposed as a logical DetNet transit router where each User Equipment (UE) and User Plane Function (UPF) (N6 interface) represents a port of the DetNet router. The 5G control plane sees the newly added Time Sensitive Communication and Time Synchronisation Function (TSCTSF) allowing external (DetNet) control plane applications to interact with the 3GPP system (that acts as a DetNet router) for the purposes of time synchronisation-related service requests, reporting time synchronisation service statuses, and exposing topology-related 3GPP domain-specific information to external applications. The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) is also

Fig. 1. System Architecture for DetNet-Enabled 3GPP and DetNet Domains.

shown in Fig. 1 to indicate the necessity to expose link and port monitoring information about the DetNet-Enabled 3GPP user plane (Uu, N3 and N9 interfaces) to the external system.

In Fig. 1 a DetNet domain is illustrated with a DetNet Router (DNR) in the data plane (aka user plane in 3GPP) and a DetNet Controller (DNC) on the domain-specific control plane to manage the router, similar to the functionalities offered by the TSCTSf and NWDAF in a DetNet-enabled 3GPP domain - just as a single system component. The DNC follows the requirements published in [6], which allows a range of DetNet data plane solutions to be controlled.

An Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based end-to-end control plane management system is needed to provision, revise and eliminate service flows across administrative and technological domains. The need of AI over traditional network modelling approaches is driven by the need to deal with the complexity of accurately predicting the network performance in each domain when provisioning a new service flow in a deterministic fashion [7]. More details on the AI-Driven Control Plane (AICP) is provided in Section II-B.

A. Data Unit Group-Enabled Data Plane

The details of the Data Unit Group (DUG)-enabled data plane are published in [8] and contributed as a draft to IETF's DetNet group [4]. The core proposition is to allow PREOF packet treatment in each DetNet router, independent of the underlying technology domain the DetNet router is placed in. Note, specific PREOF considerations for a Multi Protocol Label Switching (MPLS) over User Datagram Protocol (UDP)/IP DetNet data plane can be found in [9], which is considered to be equally applicable to the DUG-enabled IP data plane. The DUG concept borrows the core PDU Set proposition in 3GPP's eXtended Reality (XR) and Media (XRM) service feature, i.e. allowing packet treatments of a set of packets that belong to each other instead of individual treatments. Many ADUs (data an application aims to send to a remote peer, e.g. video frame

or JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)-encoded information) do not fit into a single IP packet and must be fragmented into multiple IP packets and concatenated at the receiver before being forwarded to the application. However, 3GPP's PDU Set approach only works on Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP) payload and is therefore limited to audio/video applications. The solution published in [8] and drafted in [4] brings the PDU set concept to all IP traffic (denoted as DUG to avoid confusion) and is placed into a DetNet-enabled data plane for PREOF packet treatment across an entire DUG.

To allow any IP traffic to receive PREOF treatment across packets that are from a single ADU, [4], [8] propose an IP Version 6 (IPv6) header extension, allowing application (and their libraries that generate IP packets) to tag each packet with PDU set-like information, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The header extension comes as a single Type Length Value (TLV) and the solution allows to define a long-lived service flow, as envisaged by DetNet, by utilising the IPv6 flow identifier for that purpose. This solution allows multiple DUGs to be sent over the same service flow, using the DUG flags to indicate start/end and even bursts within a DUG or for an entire DUG.

Fig. 2. DUG IPv6 Header Extension [4]

B. Network Digital Twin for Data Unit Group-Enabled DetNet Domains

The AICP illustrated in Fig. 1 builds the foundation for an end-to-end control plane of a multi-technology and multi-domain environment and has been assessed in [10] - from a standardisation perspective - to be a Network Digital Twin (NDT). The AICP in its full extent is described in detail in [11], [12] and is responsible to administer new service flows by predicting the network performance once admitted and the resulting data plane configurations in each domain. For the NDT to determine the data plane configurations, it requires the knowledge about the network topology, each node's and port's capabilities as well as live monitoring information from all nodes, ports and links. The topology information is stored in the Topology Management Function (TMF), while live monitoring data about nodes and links is stored in the Data Monitoring Function (DMF) (both part of the Data Repository, as illustrated in Fig. 1). This data is utilised by the Path Computation Element (PCE) when aiming to administer a new service flow. The prediction of the network performance based on information available in the Data Repository is conducted using AI with trained AI models made available by the Model Management component of the NDT. Once a data plane configuration has been determined by the PCE, it requests the set-up of the service flow from each domain through the respective interfaces (TSCTSf for a DetNet-enabled 3GPP domain or the DNC for a DetNet domain).

III. IMPLEMENTATION

This section provides the details on the implementation of a DUG-enabled DetNet router and its domain-internal control functions, i.e. TSCTSF and NWDAF for a 3GPP domain and a DNC for a DetNet domain. The overarching drawing is provided in Fig. 3 and forms the next three sections, which focus on the three functional interfaces between a domain and the NDT, as illustrated and described in Fig. 1 (Ntmf, Ndmf, Npce).

Fig. 3. Conceptual Implementation of a DUG-Enabled DetNet Domain

A. Data Plane DUG-Enabled DetNet Router

For the router to distinguish the packets as DUG, we introduce DUG as an extension to the IPv6 header. To comply with this requirement and to follow the guidelines on how to design IPv6 header extensions [13], [14], using TLV, a new IPv6 TLV is defined. As the order of extension headers are fixed in IPv6, the DUG-related information is added to an appropriate IPv6 header option. The main purpose of the proposed DUG TLV is for intermediate nodes to perform PREOF operation over them.

To enable DUG over DetNet Router, implementation of extended Berkeley Packet Filter (BPF) (eBPF) program is introduced. Initially called BPF, it was later expanded to include monitoring in Linux addition to packet filtering, becoming eBPF [15]. eBPF is an interpreter for Linux kernel byte code. When an application or the kernel hits a specific hook point, event-driven eBPF is launched. A number of pre-defined hooks are provided, one such hook, eXpress Data Path (XDP), is used to install a eBPF program inside the network device driver at the very beginning of the networking stack in the Linux kernel. A new socket address family called AF_XDP uses XDP to send and receive packets directly between a queue of the Network Interface Card (NIC) and a user space process [16]. The main reason for using eBPF (XDP and AF_XDP) is to improve performance. Implementation of DUG concepts utilises eBPF and suggests a way to communicate to DetNet routers the significance and associated metadata of DUGs, enabling PREOF behaviour across DUG-aware DetNet routers.

The DUG-enabled router implementation makes use of XDP hooks to implement the parsing of the DUG header and additional logging. In addition, the XDP hook establishes a set cycle time that can be used to apply simple queuing and against which all incoming packets are evaluated. Since

XDP hook lacks permanent memory storage, the ability to re-route frames to a user-space memory buffer is made possible by AF_XDP Socket (XSK) through eBPF maps. The DUG packets are kept in the maps and redirected to the AF_XDP for their access through action in the XDP hook [15]. XDP actions determines what happens to a network packet after it is processed by an eBPF program, where its types including XDP_PASS which allows packet to continue the normal network stack and XDP_REDIRECT redirects the packet to user space or another network interface.

Fig. 4. AF_XDP for DetNet Router

In the XDP hook the eBPF map `BPF_MAP_TYPE_XSKMAP` is used for redirecting packets using `bpf_redirect_map` function to the user space where packets are being processed (the AF_XDP component), as Fig. 4 suggest, which is primarily done to enable DetNet routing using the PREOF of DUG. `BPF_MAP_TYPE_XSKMAP` is an array-style map and uses key-value where keys are the indices of the network device's receive queues and values represents an XSK that is bound to the queue of the network device [15].

B. Monitoring

To provide live DUG-related networking characteristics from each DetNet router, the eBPF implementation described in the previous section has been extended to provide the data points in Table I to an NWDAF or DNC.

TABLE I
IMPLEMENTED MONITORING DATA POINTS OF DATA UNIT
GROUP-ENABLED DETNET ROUTER

Data Point	Description
dugs	Total number of DUG packets per second
ipv6_flows	The total number of IPv6 flows per second handled in active cycles
ipv6_pktcnt	The total number of IPv6 packets per second handled by DetNet router
late_packets	The ratio of packets outside a cycle over active cycles per second
link_latency	The communication latency between two DetNet routers
round_trip	The average Round Trip Time (RTT) per second between two DetNet routers

The DUG-enabled DetNet router's monitoring implementation is illustrated in Fig. 3 and is split into a monitoring agent responsible to obtain DUG-related data points from the eBPF implementation as well as an Application-Layer Probing Framework (ARIA) [17], measuring link latency and RTT

between DetNet nodes. Both the monitoring agent and ARIA write to a database representing the NWDAF and the DNC.

For ARIA [17] to measure latency and RTT values, it acts in a UDP-based client(s)/server fashion, sending small probes with a local timestamp and host name from the client to the server which the server immediately returns. If clocks on both compute hosts are synchronised, the ARIA server reports link latencies; if not, the ARIA client uses the returned probe from the server to calculate the RTT based on the timestamp it had added when sending the probe to the server.

Section III-A describes the eBPF implementation uses the kernel space to determine the bulk of monitoring-related information, for the DUG-enabled DetNet router. It is challenging to collect monitoring data within a given time frame, because eBPF applications cannot access permanent memory storage within their program environment. Temporary data storage is made possible by eBPF apps' access to eBPF maps via kernel-exposed auxiliary functions [18]. In addition to serving as a communication route between user space and kernel eBPF programs as mentioned in III-A, maps can also be used as a global coordination and monitoring tool. eBPF maps offer key/value storage capabilities and allow to monitor eBPF information per Central Processing Unit (CPU) or across all CPUs. They can be shared across separate eBPF programs that are operating at different locations inside the kernel. BPF maps are referenced within the eBPF and are defined upon loading an eBPF application (both XDP and AF_XDP).

Fig. 5. Monitoring Logic

Fig. 5 represents the monitoring flow as the incoming packets are verified to be DUG and data points mentioned in Table I are monitored using eBPF map and the packets are allowed to pass through action of the XDP hook.

C. Exposure and Service Flow Management

This section describes the implementation of the topology and capability exposure from each domain towards the NDT and the service flow management from the NDT into each domain. The software component blocks are illustrated in Fig. 6 depicting the functional software blocks and interfaces among them.

The NDT block represents the entire end-to-end AICP which obtains domain-specific topology and capability information via the Ntmf interface. This Service-Based Interface (SBI) offered by the NDT allows the TSCTSFS and DNC

Fig. 6. Exposure and Service Flow Management Implementation

to report topology and capability information in a unified fashion; the IETF drafts [19], [20] form the basis for this interface. For simplification purposes, the TSCTSFS and DNC are implemented as a single python3-based web-server with its own SBI, allowing the NDT to administer, revise and delete service flows via the Ndc interface.

The actual compute hosts on the data plane (i.e. UE, UPF and DNR) operates a dedicated DNRapi software component, which comes with its own SBI towards the TSCTSFS/DNC, i.e. Ndnr. The DNRapi, implemented in Python as a web-server, allows the TSCTSFS (in a 3GPP domain) or DNC (in a DetNet domain) to request the compute host to handle a new service flow utilising the DUG concept. The DNRapi interfaces with the compute host using python-based system i/o libraries. To load the XDP hook that implements monitoring (see Section III-B), xdp-loader (part of the xdp-tools implementation [21]) is being used. The data plane implementation comes as an AF_XDP-based object that can be directly started with a set of arguments describing the service flow (receive/send interface, service flow identifier, PREOF settings).

IV. VALIDATION

This section provides the validation results of the implementation described in Section III. The section is structured around the methodology of the methods used to validate the implementation, followed by the description of the testbed set-up, before presenting the actual results.

A. Validation Methodology

eBPF allows sand-boxed programs to run in the kernel space, enabling pre-processing of incoming IP packets before they hit the Linux networking stack. In order to verify this proposition, the DUG implementation is validated in an isolated lab testbed with identical compute hosts, and a network topology that allows stress-testing the implementation in terms of network performance Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as maximum possible throughput and link latencies/RTT and packet loss in relation to nominal link speeds. Also, the same stress tests are conducted without the DUG implementation deployed in order to fairly assess any impact of the DUG implementation on the network performance.

B. Validation Testbed Set-Up

For an end-to-end performance evaluation following the methodology outlined in the section before, a testbed set-up as illustrated in Fig. 7 has been designed. As depicted, two senders, one forwarder and one receiver compute host

have been deployed with identical NICs (Intel I210 chip), CPU (Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-1620 v3 @ 3.50GHz), and 32GB DDR3 Random Access Memory (RAM). Each link offers a 1 G connection and all nodes running an unmodified Ubuntu 24.04.1 operating system. The rationale for this specific network topology was derived from [16] (one sender and one receiver with a forwarding node interconnecting them), with the main argument of having an application-independent, routing/switching-only forwarding node to fairly assess the performance of the networking software. In addition to the network topology in [16], the network topology used in this paper is extended by two senders with 1 G links each towards the Forwarder, allowing to easily saturate the link between the Forwarder and Receiver for the purpose of stress-testing the DUG implementation on the Forwarder without potential limitations on the sender and any impact this may have in properly saturating the Forwarder→Receiver link.

Fig. 7. Validation Testbed Set-Up

To achieve the saturation on the Forwarder↔Receiver link, each sender runs a range of applications, i.e.: a single iPerf instance generating IPv6-based UDP traffic, a Scapy-based [22] application generating IPv6 packets with the optional DUG header extension, and an in-house-developed ARIA client to measure connection latencies and RTT. The same ARIA client/server pair is deployed on the Forwarder and the Receiver to report on link latency and RTT measurements.

C. Validation Results

As described in the methodology, the approach is to validate the performance characteristics of the DUG-based DetNet router in two steps, i.e. validating that there is no performance degradation when deploying the eBPF-based DUG-enabled DetNet router and then validating the PREOF behaviours; this paper focuses on the former one, while the latter step is an on-going research effort. Step 1 is achieved by measuring the maximum possible throughput between the senders and the Receiver and the RTT and iPerf-reported packet loss values over an increasing aggregated throughput. While Scapy generates a constant 0.2Mbps IPv6 traffic pattern (with the DUG header extension implemented triggering the DUG logic inside the eBPF implementation), iPerf is set up to produce plain IPv6 traffic with a manually configured UDP bandwidth. All numbers in this section are an aggregate over 23 independent measurements of 60 s-long measurements, with each application reporting measurements in 1 s windows. Note

that the actual measurements were conducted for a total of 80 s where the first ten and last ten seconds were removed before producing the plots. This allows the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) window scaling to adjust to remove any artefacts in the compute hosts to cope with the sudden network load, including the effect of stopping the network load.

Fig. 8 provides the maximum possible aggregated throughput over the 23 measurements with the DUG eBPF implementation not loaded into the kernel (denoted as “NO eBPF”). For when only the monitoring capabilities to report on the data points provided in Table I (Section III-B) are loaded as a single XDP hook per interface, the boxplot for “eBPF” is referred to. For when the DUG-enabled DetNet router is loaded (without any PREOF configured), the x-axis denotes the results as “eBPF DUG”.

Fig. 8. Aggregated Throughput Measurements with and without any Data Unit Group-Enabled DetNet Router

The results in Fig. 8 indicate that the eBPF implementation (both “eBPF” and “eBPF DUG”) does not affect the network performance. To the contrary, for the scenario where the entire DUG DetNet router software is loaded (XDP hook for monitoring and the AF_XDP and XDP hook for handling DUG-based IPv6 packets) an increase of the median achievable maximum throughput increases slightly from 940.63 Mbps to 940.648 Mbps with an almost identical lower and upper 75 percentile (upper/lower whisker), while the upper and lower quartile increases with the median. Similar results are observed and explained in [23] [24], which demonstrate that XDP can help to achieve high(er) throughput performance and low(er) latency; this is explained by eBPF being able to bypass the TCP/IP Linux kernel stack and get (as close as possible) direct access to the NIC for sending and receiving packets.

A similar observation on the network performance for whether the DUG-enabled DetNet router is loaded can be observed for the RTT results, provided in Fig. 9. The RTT results are measured with ARIA between the Forwarder and Receiver compute host when the link has been fully saturated with 940 Mbps aggregated throughput. As can be observed, the RTT, for the case when the DetNet router software is loaded, slightly decreases from a median of 1.55 ms to below 1.4 ms with a much reduced upper quantile in particular.

Lastly, the iPerf packet loss results over an increase in aggregated throughput for “NO eBPF” and “eBPF DUG” are

Fig. 9. Round Trip Time Measurements for Forwarder↔Receiver Link

TABLE II
IPERF PACKET LOSS VALIDATION RESULTS OVER AGGREGATED
THROUGHPUT FOR NO eBPF AND eBPF DUG

Aggregated Throughput [Mbps]	Packet Loss NO eBPF [%]	Packet Loss eBPF DUG [%]
918	0.00036	0
922	0.00039	0
928	0.0022	0
934	0.00272	0
940	0.66	0.65

provided in Table II. While the packet loss for “NO eBPF” started occurring at an aggregated throughput of 918 Mbps and ended up being 0.66 % for the maximum possible throughput of 940 Mbps, the “eBPF DUG” deployment demonstrated no packet loss till the maximum possible throughput was reached of an almost identical 0.65 %.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a solution and implementation of a DUG-enabled DetNet router in a NDT-driven multi-domain multi-technology setting. While the NDT fully administers service flows in an end-to-end fashion, the solution and implementation provided in the paper described the necessary details to allow a standard-compliant interaction between the NDT and the DUG-enabled DetNet router in the domains 3GPP and DetNet. The paper also validated the eBPF-based DetNet implementation in high network load scenarios to demonstrate that the implementation does not pose any performance impact when being loaded into a default Linux kernel. Typical networking performance metrics such as throughput, RTT and packet loss were measured to come to this conclusion.

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